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HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PROSTHETICS WITH LUMINEERS AND CURRENT STATUS (literature review)

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559078>

ABSTRACT

Historical background on the development of aesthetic dentistry is given and information on the introduction into dental practice of a minimally invasive technique for restoring teeth using lumineers. The types and composition of dental ceramic restorative materials and general indications and contraindications for dental treatment using lumineers are considered. It is shown that there are no scientific data describing the long-term results and complications in the application of Lumineers, and this makes research in this area extremely relevant.

Keywords: Lumineers, aesthetic dentistry, ceramic adhesive restorations.

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ИСТОРИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОТЕЗИРОВАНИЯ ЛЮМИНИРАМИ И СОСТОЯНИЕ В НАСТОЯЩЕЕ ВРЕМЯ (обзор литературы)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Дана историческая справка о развитии эстетической стоматологии, также представлены сведения о внедрении в стоматологическую практику малоинвазивной методики реставрации зубов с использованием люминиров. Рассмотрены виды и состав стоматологических керамических реставрационных материалов, а также общие показания и противопоказания к лечению зубов с использованием люминиров. Показано, что пока нет научных данных, описывающих отдаленные результаты и осложнения при применении люминиров, и это делает исследование в данном направлении чрезвычайно актуальными.

Ключевые слова: люминир, эстетическая стоматология, керамические адгезивные реставрации.

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ЛЮМИНИРЛАР БИЛАН ПРОТЕЗЛАШНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ВА ҲОЗИРГИ ВАҚТДАГИ СТАТУСИ (адабиётлар таҳлили)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Эстетик стоматологиянинг ривожланиши бўйича тарихий маълумотлар, шунингдек, стоматология амалиётида люминирлар ёрдамида тишларни тиклашнинг минимал инвазив усулини жорий этиш ҳақида маълумот берилган. Тиш керамика реставратив материалларнинг турлари ва таркиби, шунингдек люминирлар ёрдамида тишларни даволаш учун умумий кўрсатмалар кўриб чиқилади. Люминирни қўллашда узоқ муддатли натижалар ва асоратларни тавсифловчи илмий маълумотлар йўқлиги кўрсатилган ва бу ушбу соҳадаги тадқиқотларни жуда долзарб қилади.

Калит сўзлар: люминирлар, эстетик стоматология, керамик адгезив реставрациялар.

Introduction.

Metal-free ceramic restorations first began to appear in the practice of dentists in the 1980s. Until that time, the main problem in dentistry was the exact reproduction of the parameters of the prepared tooth. Subsequently, many design options for metal-ceramic crowns were developed, which were used to manufacture all-ceramic structures [1].

The modern development of dentistry is marked by the emergence of new technologies and filling materials to restore hard dental tissues, which, combined with teeth whitening techniques, makes it possible to achieve excellent aesthetic treatment results.

Main Part.

The term "aesthetics" comes from the Greek word *aesthesia*, which means "sensation" or "ability to feel". That is, aesthetics is "the ability to feel beautiful." The word "esthete" comes from a common Greek root and characterizes a person who enjoys beauty. By analogy, the term's meaning in the form of an adjective (aesthetic, aesthetical) indicates an attitude towards beauty in art or nature. In dentistry, this term should be distinguished from cosmetic, which comes from the Greek word *kosmetikos* or decoration. Aesthetic dentistry aims to improve the face's natural beauty and smile through dental procedures [6]. The aesthetic approach in dentistry has always been based on the choice of artificial shapes, colors and structures, the intrinsic beauty of which was supposed to improve the patient's appearance. "Aesthetics in dentistry is the harmonious integration of dental elements into a facial composition that meets functional requirements" (K.R. Rufenacht, 2012). Aesthetic dentistry is a field of dental science that studies the aesthetics of the maxillofacial region, its norms, anomalies and deformities, methods for their elimination and prevention.

Today, this definition is more relevant than ever. Patients' requirements for orthopedic treatment's aesthetic and functional results are increasing every year. Advanced technologies are being developed to meet these requirements and new materials are being created.

Today, this definition is more relevant than ever. Patients' requirements for orthopedic treatment's aesthetic and functional results increase every year. Advanced technologies are being developed to meet these requirements and new materials are being created.

The word aesthetics comes from the Greek "aesthesia" (in translation - "sensation" or "ability to feel"). In dentistry, this concept should be distinguished from the name "cosmetic", which also comes from the Greek "kosmos" (decoration). Thus, aesthetic dentistry aims to improve the face's natural beauty through dental manipulations [2].

The method of improving the color of discolored teeth with the help of their filling is not the main one. Aesthetic dentistry aims to produce restorations in harmony with the patient's face and mimic natural teeth and surrounding tissues as closely as possible. As a result of treatment, outsiders should not be aware of artificial teeth in the patient's mouth. However, some such pretentious patients complain that the restorations made are "ugly" just because their friends or relatives could not help but notice the new teeth "from afar"! Such patients may even ask the dentist to make changes that spoil the natural and beautiful smile. Therefore, it is important to remember specific individuals' "aesthetic values".

It is important to note that the requirements of patients for the aesthetic and functional results of dental treatment are increasing every year. To meet these requirements, new technologies and modern materials are being developed. The mass media also have an important influence, advertising the image of a successful person with a sparkling snow-white smile in the spirit of Hollywood stars.

One of the new methods of treating patients with discoloration of hard dental tissues was the introduction of lumineers into dental practice. Lumineers (Hollywood veneers, ultra veneers, veneers without preparation, nano veneers) are ultra-thin (up to 0.3 mm) ceramic constructions made in the laboratory, used without preparation of hard tissues, fixed with an adhesive system on the vestibular surface of the tooth. The use of lumineers is the method of choice among the possible methods of indirect restoration of teeth [3,5].

For the first time, the use of lumineers was suggested by the founder of the Den-Mat Corporation, Dr. Robert Ibsen (2004), using the patented kerinate ceramics Cerinate for their manufacture. For the manufacture of lumineers, various types of dental porcelain are used that have the necessary properties, in particular, glass-ceramic based on lithium disilicate for the IPS e.max Press pressing technology. This glass-ceramic chemical composition and properties, combined with a minimally invasive, gentle method of preparing the tooth for this restoration, allow achieving good results in treating patients with discoloration of the teeth of various etiologies.

Porcelain is particularly suitable for use as a restorative dental material due to its glass-like qualities and optical similarity to tooth enamel [6, 7, 9]. Sitalls (Russian - glass, crystal) is glass-ceramic materials obtained by introducing special crystallization initiators into the glass melt. When glass cools, under the action of special treatment, microcrystals appear in it, the size of which is only a few microns. This is very important since the strength of the material depends on the size of the crystals the distance between them. It is important to note that those masses commonly call ceramic or metal-ceramic are essentially glass-ceramic. Their main feature is the ability to change the coefficient of thermal expansion. Such materials have very high strength, which allows them to be used without a metal frame. Also, all materials that we call dental ceramics have a crystalline phase that provides strength, opacity, and white color. This crystalline phase - leucite (from the word "leuco" - white) of white color - is the main mineral of all glass-ceramic dental coatings and materials. The Impress 2 system uses a different phase, lithium disilicate. These glass-ceramic materials, using not leucite as the main crystalline phase but lithium disilicate, provide a qualitative leap in strength (see figure) [6, 7, 8]. providing strength, opacity, white color. This crystalline phase - leucite (from the word "leuco" - white) of white color - is the main mineral of all glass-ceramic dental coatings and materials. The Impress 2 system uses a different phase, lithium disilicate. These glass-ceramic materials, using not leucite as the main crystalline phase but lithium disilicate, provide a qualitative leap in strength (see figure) [6, 7, 8]. providing strength, opacity, white color. This crystalline phase - leucite (from the word "leuco" - white) of white color - is the main mineral of all glass-ceramic dental coatings and materials. The Impress 2 system uses a different phase, lithium disilicate. These glass-ceramic materials, using not leucite as the main crystalline phase but lithium disilicate, provide a qualitative leap in strength (see figure) [6, 7, 8].

Before finally agreeing on a treatment algorithm, the doctor must build a relationship with the patient based on mutual trust and mutual responsibility. At a level accessible to the patient, it is necessary to discuss his health problems, explain the plan of medical actions, and give objective information about the advantages, disadvantages, and costs of existing examination and treatment methods without embellishing the possibilities and without hiding possible complications. The doctor should not promise the impossible and must fulfill the promise. The doctor should be guided by the patient's interests, knowledge, and personal experience [10]. It is important to note that a doctor and a patient's perception of the "beauty of a smile" can differ significantly [11, 12, 13].

Conclusions.

The use of Lumineers for the treatment of patients with discoloration of teeth is described to a greater extent only in the media in the form of advertising, and in several domestic publications the information provided on their effectiveness is very contradictory. It is presented in the form of a brief description of their advantages over standard methods of orthopedic and therapeutic treatment. In the literature available to us, there are no scientifically substantiated data on indications and contraindications for the use of lumineers, data on the effectiveness of their use. There is also no scientific data describing the long-term results and complications of using lumineers. This makes research in this area extremely relevant.

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